

EVOLVE2CARE

D5.3 – Technical, IPR and Innovation Management

WP5 – Project Coordination and
Management

January 2025 | Version 3.0

Funded by
the European Union

Funding Acknowledgement and Disclaimer

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101158152.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Copyright message

© EVOVLE2CARE Consortium, 2024

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Document Information

Project Full Title	Engaging the Value Of Living Labs to Innovate Care And Regulatory Environments			
Acronym	EVOLVE2CARE			
Grant Agreement	101158152			
Funding Scheme	CSA – Coordination and Support Action			
Deliverable Title	D5.3 – Technical, IPR and Innovation Management			
Work Package	WP5 - Project Coordination and Management			
Delivery Date	Contractual	January 2025 (M4)	Actual	January 2025 (M4)
Status	Version 3.0 – Final			
Lead Author(s)	Konstantinos Balioukas, Adriane Thrash, Argyrios Spyridis, Paraskevi Giourka [AV]			
Contributor(s)	ALL PARTNERS			
Reviewer(s)	Vasilis Voulgarakis [VL]			
Approved by	Evdokimos Konstantinidis, Project Coordinator			
Dissemination Level	P – Public			
Type	R – Document, Report			
Keywords	Innovation Management, Advisory Board, Innovation Radar, KTH Innovation Readiness Model			

Document History

Version	Date	Edited by	Edits
0.1	10-01-2025	Konstantinos Balioukas, Paraskevi Giourka [AV]	Iterative Version 1
0.2	14-01-2025	Konstantinos Balioukas, Adriane Thrash [AV]	Iterative Version 2
0.3	20-01-2025	Konstantinos Balioukas, Argyrios Spyridis, Adriane Thrash, Paraskevi Giourka [AV]	Iterative Version 3
1.0	28-01-2025	Konstantinos Balioukas, Argyrios Spyridis, Adriane Thrash, Paraskevi Giourka [AV]	Draft Version for Review
2.0	28-01-2025	Vassilis Voulgarakis [VL]	Internal Review
2.0	30-01-2025	Konstantinos Balioukas, Adriane Thrash [AV] Despoina Petsani [AUTH]	Quality Check Ready for Submission
3.0	31-01-2025	Konstantinos Balioukas, Adriane Thrash [AV] Evdokimos Konstantinidis [AUTH]	Final Version

List of Abbreviations

BR	Business Readiness
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CR	Customer Readiness
D	Deliverable
EAB	External Advisory Board
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
EHR	Electronic Health Records
EU	European Union
FP7	Framework Programme 7
FR	Funding Readiness
GA	Grant Agreement

H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
ICI	Innovator's Capacity Indicator
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IPR	Intellectual Property Readiness
IR	Innovation Radar
IRS	Innovation Radar Survey
IRL	Innovation Readiness Level
KIC	Knowledge and Innovation Community
KER	Key Exploitable Result
LL	Living Lab(s)
MCPI	Market Creation Potential
OC	Open Call
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
T	Task
TC	Transitional Care
TMR	Team Readiness
TR	Technology Readiness
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package

List of Figures

Figure 1. AccelUp platform	19
Figure 2. External Innovations in EVOLVE2CARE's phases.....	24
Figure 3. Innovation Radar tool in the Pre-Experimentation phase	30
Figure 4. Interview and SDGs.....	31

List of Tables

Table 1. D5.3 interrelation with other Work Packages.....	9
Table 2. EVOLVE2CARE's Identified Challenges.....	14
Table 3. Trends in Transitional Care solutions	21
Table 4. Evaluation of Innovators/Researchers' LL-supported experimentation	25
Table 5. External Advisory Board Members	36
Table 6. Tentative innovation management risks.....	38

Executive Summary

This document, *Deliverable 5.3-Technical, IPR and Innovation Management*, details how the Consortium will accomplish the goals set out in Task 5.2: Technical and Innovation Management:

- Carry out technical and experimentation coordination to make sure that technological developments in the product experimentation carried out in E2C are in line with changing market demands
- Establish an External Advisory Board of Experts
- Ensure that researchers and innovators maintain ownership of their innovations
- Monitor the high innovation potential of research results and their greater impact

D5.3-Technical, IPR and Innovation Management lays down the framework and methodology for monitoring technological and innovative progress and ensuring the IPR of External Solutions developed within the context of EVOLVE2CARE. The report provides an overview of the structure to be employed for managing these solutions, assessing relevant business models and market factors, identifying possible risks, and applying mitigation measures throughout the project's two-year duration.

As this first version of the deliverable is prepared very early in the project's lifetime (M4) there is little to report in terms of results so far. However, it will illustrate the process and serve as a roadmap to guide and manage the upcoming development of external innovative solutions produced in the scope of EVOLVE2CARE. The framework and tools that will be used for understanding technological and innovation progress are defined in this first version of the document, along with the strategy for ensuring the smooth progression of the project towards the achievement of its envisioned innovation outcomes. A final version (due in September 2026, M24) will demonstrate how this framework was employed to successfully manage and advance the project's innovations.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	6
1 Introduction	9
1.1 Project Overview	9
1.2 WP5 Description.....	9
1.3 Purpose and scope of the deliverable	10
1.4 Structure	11
1.5 Potential future changes in process and/or procedures	12
2 Innovation and IPR Management in EVOLVE2CARE.....	13
2.1 EVOLVE2CARE’s mission and purpose	13
2.2 Relation to the Call this project responds to.....	13
2.3 Current challenges and pathways for innovation in the domain of Transitional Care	14
2.4 Innovative Solutions	15
2.5 Importance of Collaborative Innovation through Living Labs.....	16
3 Project Innovations	18
3.1 Types of Innovation in EVOLVE2CARE.....	18
3.2 EVOLVE2CARE’s Internal Innovations - AccelUp and Training Programs.....	18
3.2.1 AccelUp.....	18
3.2.2 Training Programs for a) Living Labs, and b) Innovators/Researchers.....	19
3.3 External Innovations.....	20
4 Methodology for Monitoring Innovation	25
4.1 Process for managing innovation for external experimentation in LL residencies.....	25
4.2 Methodology for managing innovation for external experimentation in LL residencies.....	26
4.3 The Innovation Radar (IR) Methodology.....	26
4.4 The KTH Innovation Readiness Model.....	28
4.5 Project’s Methodological Approach	29
4.5.1 Application and Initial Self-Assessment	29
4.5.2 Evaluation of Applications by Consortium Committee.....	29

4.5.3	Follow-on Interview for Goal-Setting with KPIs	30
4.5.4	During the Residency: Mid-term Status Check.....	31
4.5.5	End of Residency Interview and Feedback.....	32
5	IPR Management.....	33
5.1	IPR in EVOLVE2CARE.....	33
5.2	IPR in EVOLVE2CARE’s external innovations.....	33
6	Advisory Board Activation	35
6.1	Recruiting & Selection	35
6.2	Expectations	35
6.3	External Advisory Board Member Profiles	36
7	Technical, Innovation and IPR Progress, and Risks for their Exploitation.....	38
8	Conclusions, Risks, and next steps.....	39

1 Introduction

1.1 Project Overview

EVOLVE2CARE focuses on HealthTech experimentation practice to standardise and enhance the collaboration between Living Labs and innovators in the context of the Transitional Care sector. Challenges ranging from aging population to complexity of medical conditions and regulatory frameworks bring a growing recognition of the importance of experimentation practises. By subjecting innovations to real-world environments that involve end-users and stakeholders, EVOLVE2CARE provides innovators with access to services for testing and validating research and products.

The project focuses on three Use Cases (UC): i) Hospital discharge management; ii) Homecare monitoring solutions; and iii) Aging population & care transitions, engaging stakeholders across the whole value chain to examine complexities, barriers and enablers that regulatory framework poses to the development and commercialisation of healthcare innovations.

1.2 WP5 Description

The primary aim of WP5, led by AUTH, is to guarantee the successful implementation of the project. Its specific objectives include:

- Overseeing and managing the overall execution of the project.
- Ensuring adherence to the legal, contractual, financial, and reporting obligations outlined by Horizon Europe and the European Commission.
- Delivering the project on schedule and within budget while promoting effective communication between participants and work packages (WPs) and maintaining correspondence with the European Commission.
- Addressing technical, intellectual property rights (IPR), innovation management, and compliance with the data management plan.

The horizontal nature of WP5 (Project Coordination and Management) and subsequently T5.2 and its respective deliverables, including D5.3, creates a cross-cutting relation to activities throughout EVOLVE2CARE. Specifically, D5.3 (report on activities carried out in T5.2) is directly related to WP2: T2.3, T2.4; WP3: T3.1, T3.4, and WP4: T4.2.

Table 1. D5.3 interrelation with other Work Packages

TASK/WP	TITLE & DESCRIPTION	RELEVANCE
---------	---------------------	-----------

WP2: T2.2	LLs, Innovators & Researchers Scouting and Selection	Ensure that all IPR remains with the innovators/researchers during their collaboration with the Living Labs.
WP2: T2.3	Training Program for Living Labs	Training provided to Living Lab practitioners and managers, helping them to expand their offerings and leverage their resources to become more commercially-minded, sustainable operating entities.
WP2: T2.4	Training Program for Innovators & Researchers	Training provided to the innovator/researcher community on various aspects of innovation, business, and IPR, especially as these relate to working with Living Labs
WP3: T3.1	Use Case Execution of Experimentation Svcs, Monitoring & Evaluation	Assess the experimentation results based on goals set between LLs and innovators.
WP3: T3.4	Evaluation of the Commercialization Potential for Innovators	Use the IR and KTh tools to evaluate the innovators selected for LL services via the OC, for innovation, commercialization, and regulatory aspects; conduct interviews; provide feedback report.
WP4: T4.2	Exploitation and IPR of AccelUp	Oversee innovation progress of AccelUp, its exploitation/rollout, and IPR.

1.3 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

D5.3-Technical, IPR and Innovation Management, entitled “Technical, IPR and Innovation Management (v1)”, defines and presents EVOLVE2CARE’s strategy and means for technical and innovation coordination, as tied to the actions laid out in Task 5.2(Technical and Innovation Management).

D5.3-Technical, IPR and Innovation Management provides the framework for achieving and reporting the consortium’s progress on the following areas. Future versions of this deliverable (*D5.6-Technical, IPR and Innovation Management - Final* in September 2026 ,M24) will present accomplishments and detail any changes or necessary corrections in these matters, as the project advances. The key aims of Task 5.2(Technical and Innovation Management) are:

1. Coordinate efforts to assess and manage the technological and innovative potential and readiness of solutions introduced to the project via the utilisation of Living Lab services accessed through the Open Call (external innovations) and ensure they are aligned with market needs;

2. Provide tools for addressing the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) of the external innovators and Living Labs;
3. Incorporate feedback and guidance from the Advisory Board regarding innovation issues that arise during the project's lifetime.
4. Identify and elaborate conclusions on the overall process of innovation management within the project.

1.4 Structure

D5.3-Technical, IPR and Innovation Management is structured in eight (8) chapters as follows:

- Chapter 1: Introduction: Overview of this document - Details the Aim of the Deliverable, the Structure of the Deliverable, and the Dependencies with other WPs and Tasks, and a statement regarding the potential for changes in process and/or procedures in upcoming activities.
- Chapter 2: Innovation and IPR Management in EVOLVE2CARE - Provides a summary of the context, purpose and goals of the EVOLVE2CARE project, the importance of stakeholder involvement in transforming transitional care, and the role of Living Labs as key drivers of innovation.
- Chapter 3: EVOLVE2CARE's Innovations - Discusses the Internal (innovations produced by the project) and External (innovations tested in the Living Labs as facilitated by EVOLVE2CARE) solutions that emerge from EVOLVE2CARE and provides context from real world examples.
- Chapter 4: Methodology for Monitoring Innovation - Details the rationale for managing innovation, available tools and processes, and the particular framework that EVOLVE2CARE will implement.
- Chapter 5: Methodology for IPR Management - Presents the value of correct management of IPR and EVOLVE2CARE's process for ensuring that innovators/researchers maintain control of their IPR.
- Chapter 6: Advisory Board Activation - Coverage of the Advisory Board, including individual members' activities and profiles, plans for leveraging it to maximise the project's outputs, and its relation to the Ethics Advisory Board.
- Chapter 7: Technical and Innovation Progress - Presents the progress of the innovations according to the monitoring framework explained in Chapter 2, along with identified risks and mitigation actions so far.
- Chapter 8: Conclusions - A summary of the steps taken so far, with associated conclusions and recommendations.

1.5 Potential future changes in process and/or procedures

This report is generated at the beginning of the project's lifetime in January 2025(M4), and the activities which it covers have yet to commence. The framework, processes and procedures laid out in this document have been designed based upon the Partners' extensive experience with similar activities involving researchers, innovators, startups, Living Labs and other innovation actors. Nevertheless, it is possible that adjustments will need to be made once the activities begin, should circumstances reveal gaps or unanticipated needs that must be covered. In this case, the consortium will follow correct internal procedures to decide how to respond, and what (if any) new measures need to be enacted. Any such changes will be fully documented and reported in due course, at the latest in September 2026(M24) with the final version of this deliverable.

2 Innovation and IPR Management in EVOLVE2CARE

2.1 EVOLVE2CARE's mission and purpose

Healthcare is evolving rapidly, spurred by a myriad of social, economic and environmental challenges, and the processes, products and services that aim to solve them. EVOLVE2CARE's mission is to understand and reveal the drivers and barriers that impact the development of innovative solutions for healthcare in Europe. The primary objective is to address delays in development, sales, and adoption of solutions which stem from the rapid rate of innovation in HealthTech. Such delays can be caused by market forces or by slower responses from regulatory frameworks, and the resulting asynchronicity can lead to uncertainty for manufacturers and delays in getting products to market.

2.2 Relation to the [Call](#) this project responds to

EVOLVE2CARE is a response to the Call Topic, specifically designed to stimulate experimentation practices, and foster interconnected, inclusive, and efficient innovation ecosystems. In this context, E2C's innovation framework encompasses the following principles:

1. **Interconnected:** By facilitating the digital innovation of the healthcare sector, we are streamlining processes and ensuring that information, resources, and innovations are seamlessly shared across regions.
2. **Inclusive:** By focusing on transitional care, we are ensuring that patients, their families, and carers are at the center of our innovation strategy. This inclusive approach ensures that the unique needs, challenges, and aspirations of these stakeholders are addressed, fostering a healthcare ecosystem that is truly patient-centric and inclusive of all.
3. **Efficient:** Efficiency is the lynchpin of our innovation strategy, and our use of Living Labs (LLs) underscores this commitment. The hands-on, practical nature of LLs ensures that solutions are tested, refined, and validated in real world settings, ensuring that they are not only technically sound but also practically impactful. This approach drastically reduces the time-to-market, ensures relevance, and guarantees that our innovations are both efficient and effective.

2.3 Current challenges and pathways for innovation in the domain of Transitional Care

Transitional Care (TC) encompasses the practices and processes used to maintain continuity as patients move between different stages and settings of care. TC is a key link in the healthcare value chain, and relies upon a vast array of data and information gathered and exchanged between devices, systems, and word-of-mouth. It involves individuals, institutions, regulatory bodies and companies. As the population ages, already strained healthcare systems are in great need of innovations that can streamline and improve the TC landscape to ensure the provision of effective services and care.

Transitional Care refers to the coordination and continuity of healthcare during transitions from one healthcare setting to another or to home, involving healthcare practitioners and settings as patients' conditions and care needs evolve during the course of a chronic or acute illness.

Transitional Care systems are burdened by a wide range of inconsistencies and challenges, such as poor communication, medication errors, lack of education for patients and caregivers, insufficient follow-up care, limited access to services, difficult or underpaid working conditions, non-compliance with regulatory or other protocols, and financial or insurance barriers. Addressing these challenges requires a coordinated approach, better care planning, patient education, integration of services, and robust support systems to ensure patients safely navigate transitions and avoid readmissions.

The safe and effective care of citizens has been established as an EU Priority, codified in the [2022 European Care Strategy](#). In the face of increasing demand and demographic shifts from an aging population, innovation in services to transform care is one key element of this Strategy.

EVOLVE2CARE has identified four challenges that are specific to Transitional Care:

Table 2. EVOLVE2CARE's Identified Challenges

TECHNOLOGY	Challenge #1: Transitional care technologies often need to integrate with existing healthcare systems and electronic health records. Achieving interoperability can be technically challenging, requiring seamless data exchange while adhering to standardized formats.
CORPORATE	Challenge #2: Experimentation in complex ecosystems, such as transitional care that involves a wide network of stakeholders, requires substantial

	resources, especially when there are inconsistent assessment practices.
SOCIETAL	Challenge #3: Engaging patients in experimentation can be challenging due to factors such as variations in techno-literacy and access to technology, ethical concerns, and fear of change. Furthermore, healthcare practices and patient behaviors can vary based on cultural, socio-economic, and regional factors. Designing technologies that align with these nuances is crucial for successful experimentation and adoption.
REGULATORY	Challenge #4: HealthTech innovations are subject to a complex web of regulations, which can vary from country to country. Depending on the risk level and intended use, health devices may fall under different regulatory categories, each with its own set of requirements. Navigating these regulations, which can vary across jurisdictions, poses a significant challenge to innovators and researchers aiming to conduct experiments and trials.

2.4 Innovative Solutions

Each of these challenges can be addressed with the proper application of innovative technologies and processes, such as digitalization. In the European context, digitalization aims to modernize the care sector by integrating cutting-edge technologies into healthcare systems. The ultimate goal is to increase efficiency, enhance accessibility, improve care quality, and address workforce challenges in the face of an aging population. By embracing digital technologies, the EU hopes to create a more sustainable, person-centered, and efficient care ecosystem that benefits both caregivers and recipients. Innovative digital technologies and solutions encompass the following:

- Telemedicine and telehealth leverage digital platforms for remote patient services such as consultations, diagnosis and communication.
- Care Management Platforms connect patients with caregivers, clinicians and healthcare professionals for more efficient communication, scheduling, and monitoring of care needs.
- Wearable Devices and other Assistive Technologies that utilise sensors and voice activation can help carers and providers better address the needs of patients.
- Electronic Health Records (EHR) Widespread adoption and coordination of EHR and Data Sharing can streamline the availability of patient information across

different settings (hospitals, home care, specialists), reducing errors, ensuring continuity of care, and improving overall service delivery.

- AI & Data Analytics are being increasingly integrated into care management systems to improve efficiency, predict care needs, and personalize treatment. AI can quickly and efficiently analyze data from wearable devices or home sensors, or enable fast integration of patient information when changing locations.
- Health surveillance tools can track the spread of diseases, monitor healthcare resource usage, and help plan for future care needs.
- Digital inclusion, ensuring that vulnerable groups such as the elderly, people with disabilities, and those with low digital literacy can access and benefit from digital care services must be encouraged and supported in order to guarantee that everyone has access to necessary technologies, the skills to use them, and support if needed.
- Data privacy and security, particularly as systems are more connected, is crucial in solutions addressing transitional care. New technologies such as blockchain can be harnessed to ensure users' privacy, security and control of their sensitive data, while enabling the flow of information for improved care.

2.5 Importance of Collaborative Innovation through Living Labs

Researchers and others who are using digital tools and processes to develop new technologies and products can benefit greatly from a co-creation cycle that actively engages end users, decision makers, regulators, innovators, and other relevant stakeholders along the entire continuum of care, early in the experimentation process. EVOLVE2CARE aims to provide that access by leveraging a diverse marketplace of experimentation spaces - known as Living Labs - and their associated infrastructures and networks. Such a collaborative approach can lead to the faster release of new solutions, while shedding light in real-time on some of the challenges that arise during the testing of innovative HealthTech solutions.

Health and Wellbeing-focused Living Labs offer a wide range of resources that are vital to the iterative process. Tools including test beds, prototyping facilities, data, and cutting-edge hardware and software can be used for faster technological development. Access to panels of community members allows researchers to test their hypotheses and products with real potential end-users. This approach to innovation yields

products and services that are more responsive to user needs and thus more likely to succeed.

3 Project Innovations

3.1 Types of Innovation in EVOLVE2CARE

The innovations developed in EVOLVE2CARE are categorised as **Internal Innovations** (that is, produced and advanced by the project itself, related to EVOLVE2CARE's KERs) and **External Innovations** "Experimentations" (solutions belonging to researchers that are tested in the Living Labs as chosen through the Open Call). This chapter will address each type of innovation and discuss the plans and/or services we will develop for each one. T5.2 (Technical and Innovation Management) covers only the management of External Innovations (See section 1.3). However, Internal Innovations are addressed in this section to provide context to EVOLVE2CARE's overall innovative structure.

3.2 EVOLVE2CARE's Internal Innovations – AccelUp and Training Programs

3.2.1 AccelUp

The key Internal innovation to be developed in EVOLVE2CARE is AccelUp¹. Originally spun-out from the H2020 VITALISE Action², (GA 101007990), this platform provides a full-service marketplace for Living Labs to bid on innovation projects that are posted to the platform.

¹ <https://accelup.eu/home>

² <https://vitalise-project.eu/>

Figure 1. AccelUp platform

AccelUp is an integral part of the EVOLVE2CARE Action. It serves as the backbone for our entire process of matching researchers and innovators with Living Labs, and ultimately will provide a crucial connecting point for all stakeholders in innovation ecosystems (innovators, startups, Living Labs, investors, policymakers, and end users). As such, it will be developed, managed, and leveraged throughout the project, and is not covered under the scope of T5.2(Technical, and Innovation Management). Deliverables reporting directly on AccelUp include *D1.3-EVOLVE2CARE Action Plan [WP1-EVOLVE2CARE experimentation space framework*, due in June 2025(M9) (a), and in April 2026(M19)(b)], *D2.1 - AccelUP Experimentation Space Infrastructure [WP2-Matching AccelUP Experimentation Space and Services with Innovators and Researchers* due in September 2025(M12)(a), and in September 2026(M24)(b)], *D3.3 - Standardization, Scalability, Replicability and Business Model [WP3 (Set Up of AccelUP experimentation Space and Services Execution, Lessons Learnt and Best) practices* due in September 2026(M24)], and *D4.3 - Clustering with EIT KICs projects and relevant initiatives [WP4(EVOLVE2CARE 's People-Centric Experimentation Ecosystem Outreach, Sustainability and Clustering)*, due in September 2026(M24).

3.2.2 Training Programs for a) Living Labs, and b) Innovators/Researchers

EVOLVE2CARE will implement two separate training programs, one targeting Living Labs and one aimed at Innovators/Researchers. These training programs will combine live online sessions with recorded content and material, and can potentially be scaled to a wider audience following the project's termination. Each program will be delivered through a specific Task (T2.3 Training Program for Living Labs and T2.4 Training Program for Innovators and Researchers, respectively) with its own reporting structure.

As noted in section 2.2 above, T5.2 (Technical, and Innovation Management) is related to these tasks as a feeder/receiver of input but does not cover them per se. Deliverables reporting on the Training Programs include *D2.3-Training Program for Living Labs* due in November 2025(M14), and *D2.4-Training Program for Innovators/Researchers* due in November 2025(M14).

The complete and validated mapping of EVOLVE2CARE's main innovations and the consequent Key Exploitable Results will be elaborated in detail on *D4.2 -Exploitation and IPR Management*, due in September 2026 (M24).

3.3 External Innovations

The overall goal of T5.2(Technical, and Innovation Management) as it concerns innovation management of the External Innovations is to [monitor the high innovation potential of research results and their greater impact towards EVOLVE2CARE's goals](#); the overall goal of managing IPR for External Innovations is to [ensure that researchers and innovators maintain ownership of their innovations](#).

EVOLVE2CARE's concentration on transitional care dictates that we recruit innovators who are pursuing innovative solutions in our three Use Case areas: a) hospital discharge management, b) home care monitoring, and c) aging population and care transitions. As noted previously, these areas are inherently intertwined with multiple industries (e.g., medicine, technology, pharmaceuticals, and insurance/finance), each of which faces multiple unique challenges and opportunities. EVOLVE2CARE's coordinated approach between innovators and Living Labs will facilitate the testing, research and/or validation of various solutions to answer these needs by sponsoring ten (10) Innovator Residencies at certified Living Labs in Europe. Through an Open Call, we will award individuals or teams with vouchers covering up to €5000 worth of LL services to support the validation of their healthtech product or service.

In order to correctly design, build, and deploy solutions that address these challenges, researchers and innovators require extensive contact and feedback with stakeholders and data from across the value chain. These will be accessed through the Living Labs, which they will be matched with in accordance with their specific development needs. As discussed in section 2.1.3, (challenges and pathways for innovation), there is potentially a great deal of overlap in solutions responding to our use cases, and some products may address all three of the UCs. While the Application and Evaluation phase has yet to begin, a short summary of indicative trends for our three Use Cases reveals a wide range of possibilities:

Table 3. Trends in Transitional Care solutions

Use Case 1: Hospital Discharge Management		
Trend	Impact	Innovation (Technology or Process)
Hospitals are increasingly considering social determinants of health (SDOH) when planning discharge, recognizing that income, housing, access to transportation, social support etc. can significantly affect recovery and adherence to treatment plans.	Hospitals can help ensure that patients have the resources and environment they need to recover successfully, reducing readmissions and improving overall health outcomes	Training for Discharge planners; integrated EHRs, telehealth systems
AI and predictive analytics are being used to predict which patients may be at higher risk for readmission or complications, and guide discharge planning accordingly.	AI-driven insights can help prioritize follow-up care, flag patients who need extra attention, and optimize resource allocation in discharge planning, improving outcomes and reducing hospital readmissions.	SW integration with EHRs and Discharge Mgmt. protocols
Blockchain for Secure Data Sharing can improve the security and interoperability of discharge-related health data, making it easier to share patient information between hospitals, outpatient clinics, and post-acute care providers securely.	Blockchain enhances data security and transparency, facilitating better communication and continuity of care across providers and reducing the risk of data breaches or errors.	SW integration with EHRs
Use Case 2: Home Care Monitoring		
Trend	Impact	Innovation (Technology or

		Process)
Integration of AI and Machine Learning is enhancing home care monitoring by analyzing large amounts of health data in real time to generate predictive insights. AI can help identify patterns in patient behavior, monitor health trends, and predict complications.	AI algorithms can predict when a patient may experience an exacerbation of their condition (e.g., heart failure or COPD), alerting healthcare providers to intervene early and reduce the risk of serious complications or hospital readmissions.	SW integrated with wearable or connect (“smart”) home devices and systems (IoT)
The adoption of wearable health technology, such as fitness trackers, smartwatches, and biosensors, is on the rise. These wearables are capable of tracking various health metrics like heart rate, ECG, activity levels, sleep patterns, and even stress.	Wearables provide patients with an easy way to monitor their health continuously, while healthcare providers can track these metrics remotely, enabling more personalized care and early detection of potential issues.	Sensor (IoT) based devices with S/W integration, compatibility with telehealth systems and devices
The push for health data interoperability allows home care monitoring systems to seamlessly share patient data with electronic health records (EHRs) and other healthcare systems.	Data collected through home monitoring devices can be integrated into the patient’s broader care plan, allowing healthcare providers to have a complete view of the patient’s health and make more informed decisions.	S/W with GDPR and other associated compliance, integrated with devices and wearables
Use Case 3: Aging population and care transitions.		
Trend	Impact	Innovation (Technology or Process)
Implementation of fall detection technologies and fall prevention systems is increasing. These include	Falls are a leading cause of injury among the elderly, and these technologies help reduce the risk, enabling older adults to maintain	S/W with GDPR and other associated compliance, integrated with

<p>wearables, motion sensors, smart home devices, and even AI-driven systems that can detect a fall or risk of falling.</p>	<p>mobility and independence, and providing caregivers with the ability to respond quickly in the event of a fall.</p>	<p>devices and wearables, compatible with emergency services</p>
<p>Palliative and hospice care models are becoming more widely integrated into aging population care management. These care options focus on symptom relief, improving quality of life, and providing support for families.</p>	<p>This trend allows older adults with life-limiting conditions to receive compassionate care at home, ensuring that their final years are as comfortable and fulfilling as possible, while also providing emotional and psychological support for families.</p>	<p>New medicines and therapies, combined with responsive policy measures; insurance protocols could also be examined; legal processes and documents associated with end-of-life</p>
<p>Policy reform and financial support for long-term care are becoming critical as more people live longer. Governments and insurance providers are exploring new ways to finance long-term care, including improved reimbursement for home and community-based services.</p>	<p>These reforms will make long-term care more accessible and affordable for families and reduce the financial burden on both patients and healthcare systems, making it easier for older adults to age with dignity.</p>	<p>New models for financial and/or insurance industry, faster approval for drug trials, training and support for home-health care workforce</p>

The external innovations will take place during Phase 2 and Phase 3:

Figure 2. External Innovations in EVOLVE2CARE's phases

4 Methodology for Monitoring Innovation

Managing Innovation Potential requires attention to a multitude of factors related to the technology and business aspects of the proposed project. As noted earlier, the overall goal of T5.2(Technical, and Innovation Management) as it concerns managing the External Innovations is to monitor the high innovation potential of research results and their greater impact towards EVOLVE2CARE’s goals.

4.1 Process for managing innovation for external experimentation in LL residencies

EVOLVE2CARE will perform evaluations of the external innovation projects at five distinct junctures:

Table 4. Evaluation of Innovators/Researchers' LL-supported experimentation

When	What	Method	Result	Use
Open Call phase	All submitted applications	Internal criteria (Consortium)	Top scorers accepted for funded residencies	Inform E2Cs internal processes, as well as T1.1, T 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4
After Selection	All accepted innovators	Adapted version of Innovation Radar	Projects selected for residency will do a self-evaluation	Inform E2Cs internal processes, as well as T1.1, T 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4
During 1st Interview	All innovators in residency	Define goals and KPIs for residency concerning Product, Market, Regulatory	KPIs will provide concrete indicators of progress during residency	Inform T1.1, T3.2, 3.4
During 2nd interview	All innovators in residency	Check KPI completion, general feedback on residency	Assess effectiveness of residency	Inform T1.1, T3.2, 3.4
Exit from Residency	All innovators completing	KTH tool will assess progress with objective	Assess effectiveness of residency	Inform T1.1, T3.2, 3.4

	residency	criteria		
--	-----------	----------	--	--

4.2 Methodology for managing innovation for external experimentation in LL residencies

EVOLVE2CARE’s Innovation Management Methodology supports the goals of T3.4 (Evaluation and advancement of the commercialization potential for Innovators and Researchers [M14-M24] and assists those applicants to set goals for a) product validation, b) market validation, c) compliance with the regulatory landscape. As noted above, the methodology comprises a set of questionnaires, interviews, KPIs, and assessments using the KTH Innovation Readiness Level and Innovation Radar tools in specific phases. Following is an overview of the tools and processes we will employ.

4.3 The Innovation Radar (IR) Methodology

Designed to identify promising innovations and the organizations driving them, the Innovation Radar (IR)³ methodology is a framework used to assess the innovation potential of projects funded by European Union (EU) programs, notably the Framework Programme 7 (FP7) and Horizon 2020⁴. Its introduction in May 2014, initially within the context of FP7 ICT project evaluations, established it as a key source of actionable intelligence on various innovations originating from EU-funded research and development efforts⁵. The IR has been consistently applied throughout the Horizon 2020 program.

The core of the IR framework is the Innovation Radar Survey (IRS), a survey instrument administered by an independent expert at three distinct junctures during a project's lifespan. The IRS serves to pinpoint exploitable project innovations and identify up to three key organizations best positioned to facilitate their commercialization. The ongoing development of the portal, notably the integration and application of the Market Creation Potential Indicator (MCPI)⁶ that was added to the Innovation Potential

³ <https://www.innoradar.eu/>

⁴ De Prato, G., Nepelski, D., & Piroli, G. (2015a). Innovation Radar: Identifying Innovations and Innovators with High Potential in ICT FP7, CIP & H2020 Projects. Seville: JRC.

⁵ <https://www.innoradar.eu/spotlight>

⁶ Market Creating Innovations in the EU Framework Programme, JRC Technical Reports, 2020. Accessed online on 13.03.2022: https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC121066/ir_mcpi.pdf

Indicator or IPI, and the Innovator's Capacity Indicator or ICI, reflects a deepening comprehension of the dynamics of technology transfer and commercialization.

Beyond this assessment framework, the IR operates as a dissemination and discovery platform for innovative products and technologies via the Innovation Radar Portal. E2C's use of the IR criteria will allow us to acquaint researchers/innovators with IR resources and services, thus exposing it to a wider audience or potential beneficiaries. This online resource provides concise summaries of EU-funded innovations at various stages of market readiness. A sophisticated search function allows users to identify EU-funded companies based on diverse parameters, including geographic location, technological domain, female leadership, and alignment with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This search capability enhances the portal's utility as a resource for investors, researchers, and policymakers. The portal also hosts the IR Prize competition, which provides recognition to companies whose technologies have undergone evaluation using the IR methodology. Furthermore, in partnership with dealroom.eu⁷, the platform offers a dedicated space providing access to financing opportunities for companies seeking to propel their development further. In April 2024 the 10th edition of the Innovation Radar formed a partnership with 'The Europas 100 Hottest Startups Awards' and also reinforced its IR Bridge Project, to foster connections between EU-funded innovators, European investors, and policymakers in member states.

Innovation Radar in EVOLVE2CARE:

EVOLVE2CARE will adapt the IR evaluation criteria for our purposes and request that each project which is accepted for residency use it to perform a self-evaluation, in the beginning of the process. These results will be used to inform much of E2C's internal processes and specific tasks such as T1.1(Drivers and Barriers for the development of innovations), T2.2(LLs, Innovators and Researchers Scouting and selection), T3.1(Use Case Execution of Experimentation Services, Monitoring and Evaluation), T3.2(Knowledge sharing, exchange of best practices, and policy recommendations), and T3.4(Evaluation and advancement of the commercialization potential for Innovators/Researchers), as well as final reporting on overall achievements of the project.

⁷ <https://dealroom.co/>

4.4 The KTH Innovation Readiness Model

The KTH Innovation Readiness Level™ (IRL) model was developed collaboratively by KTH Royal Institute of Technology⁸, and is widely used to examine various stages of innovation. The model's ongoing evolution encourages continuous input and refinement from various stakeholders within the KTH innovation ecosystem, such as the inaugural KTH Innovation Readiness Level Summit⁹ which took place in Stockholm July 2024, bringing the community of users together exchanging experiences from 1000 adopting organizations around the world. Such a cooperative, iterative approach to the tool's evolution ensures that it is responsive to the rapidly changing landscape of technology, entrepreneurship and innovation

The KTH Innovation Readiness Level Components

The KTH Innovation Readiness Level™ (IRL) model constitutes a structured methodology for evaluating innovation projects, particularly those at early stages and based on technological advancements. The model employs six distinct readiness levels—Customer Readiness (CR), Technology Readiness (TR), Business Readiness (BR), Intellectual Property Readiness (IPR), Team Readiness (TMR), and Funding Readiness (FR)—to provide a comprehensive assessment of project maturity through a scale of 1 to 9 with of respective criteria for each one of the six categories. This framework facilitates the systematic monitoring of a business concept's development status and informs the strategic planning of subsequent steps aimed at enhancing its overall maturity. The model's generic design allows for its application across diverse technological sectors, regardless of the specific business concept. The integrated assessment results are graphically represented through a spider diagram providing a concise visual summary of the project's performance across the six dimensions.

⁸ <https://kthinnovationreadinesslevel.com/about/>

⁹ <https://www.healthdatasweden.eu/event/kth-innovation-readiness-level-summit/>

KTH in EVOLVE2CARE:

EVOLVE2CARE will use the KTH tool at the end of Innovators' residencies. These results will be used to inform much of EVOLVE2CARE's internal processes and specific tasks such as T1.1(Drivers and Barriers for the development of innovations), T3.2(Knowledge sharing, exchange of best practices, and policy recommendations), and T3.4 (Evaluation and advancement of the commercialization potential for Innovators/Researchers), as well as final reporting on overall achievements of the project.

4.5 Project's Methodological Approach

4.5.1 Application and Initial Self-Assessment

Innovator/Researchers who respond to the Open Call for funded support will include various parameters in their application materials. If accepted, they will be requested to perform a self-assessment of their project's Innovation Potential. EVOLVE2CARE will provide a template based on respective Indicators (Innovation Potential Indicator - IPI) taken from the Innovation Radar Survey. These self-assessments will be shared with EVOLVE2CARE and allow us to achieve the following:

- Measure the innovation and commercialization levels of the innovations they wish to test in the LLs, along with the regulatory challenges they perceive to be significant. This will generate an overview (T3.4 Evaluation and advancement of the commercialization potential for Innovators/Researchers) of the type and status of HealthTech researchers that we have reached and who desire to access LLs, as well as an understanding of the possible barriers they face offering insight for T1.1. and T3.2.
- Provide insights for better matchmaking with LLs (WP1 EVOLVE2CARE experimentation space framework, T2.1, 2.1, T3.1, T3.3, T3.4, T4.2)
- Establish a preliminary outlook of the innovation, impact, scalability and the challenges pertaining to their objectives T3.4, T4.2)
- Estimate the current IPR status of the applicants' innovations

4.5.2 Evaluation of Applications by Consortium Committee

After the end of the submission deadline, a committee composed of consortium partner representatives will review and evaluate the materials and conclude with:

1. An Internal Report summarizing the outcomes of the applications

2. A short list of the applicants who meet the eligibility requirements and score highest on evaluative criteria
3. Feedback to the Applicants on their results
4. In case of a positive decision to fund the project, Innovators will be requested to perform the IR-based Self-Assessment (provided by E2C).

Figure 3. Innovation Radar tool in the Pre-Experimentation phase

4.5.3 Follow-on Interview for Goal-Setting with KPIs

Once projects are accepted, an interview will be scheduled. In the first part the interviewer(s) will use the submitted material to confirm TRL as well as innovation maturity, market potential, team strength, regulatory challenges and evaluate specific aspects relevant to each project. Following that both interviewer and interviewee will define specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) goals¹⁰ for the LL experimentation period, recorded as KPIs. Those goals will involve the following areas, adjusted as appropriate for each proposed experiment:

- a) Product Validation: Define specific product features or functionalities to be tested and validated in the LL environment.
- b) Market Validation: Identify target customer segments and define metrics for measuring market acceptance and user feedback.
- c) Compliance with the Regulatory Landscape: With the help of the Interviewer the Innovators will outline specific regulatory requirements to be addressed.

¹⁰ Doran, G. T. (1981). "There's a S.M.A.R.T. way to write management's goals and objectives" (PDF). Management Review. 70 (11): 35–36.

A simple KPI template will be used to assist the innovators to guide their steps and measure progress. The KPI process will not affect the experiments or work outcomes that are pursued during the residency, but should prepare the innovators to steer their efforts more effectively, and consider related parameters, e.g., Product Development, Regulatory Processes, Investor Awareness, Market Research.

SDG information: Information regarding the impact of each project that is leveraging the EVOLVE2CARE residency will also be gathered during the residency. Integrating the SDGs into research projects offers several key benefits. Firstly, it provides a structured approach for demonstrating the societal impact of research outcomes, a factor increasingly prioritized by funding agencies and policymakers. Secondly, alignment with the SDGs can enhance the relevance and visibility of research within broader societal contexts. Finally, and perhaps most importantly, explicitly linking research to the SDGs ensures that projects contribute to addressing real-world challenges and fostering sustainable development. While all of the projects are expected to align with SDG #3 (Good Health & Wellbeing), it is likely that there are other SDGs that may also be impacted, such as SDG #8 (Decent Work & Economic Growth) or SDG #11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities). Therefore, consideration of the SDGs is crucial for maximizing the impact and societal relevance of EVOLVE2CARES External Innovation research endeavours.

Figure 4. Interview and SDGs

4.5.4 During the Residency: Mid-term Status Check

At the mid-way point of the residency a status check will be made to ensure that the process is proceeding without any obstacles for the engaged parties. During this we will check for:

- a) the speed of progress between matched LLs and Innovators
- b) deviations from the originally approved process
- c) the IPR ownership of the innovation

Check-ups can be made via scheduled calls or written communication (email, text, etc.) and the results will be collected for the final report.

4.5.5 End of Residency Interview and Feedback

A Final Interview will be conducted with the Innovators/Researchers to check their achievements and KPI progress during the residency. The KTH tool will be used to perform an Investment Readiness assessment, and a cumulative report will be generated with findings to support T3.4 (Evaluation and advancement of the commercialization potential for Innovators/Researchers) - to be reported by AV in D3.4 in September 2026 (M24).

5 IPR Management

5.1 IPR in EVOLVE2CARE

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management is particularly important in EVOLVE2CARE activities as it involves multiple entities and organizations. EVOLVE2CARE will establish clear agreements on ownership, usage, and commercialization of the research outcomes to define how patents, copyrights, or trademarks will be shared or licensed. It will ensure that all parties' contributions are properly recognized and their respective interests are protected, fostering a foundation of trust and encouraging open collaboration while minimizing the risk of legal disputes. EVOLVE2CARE will define rights and responsibilities upfront, and IPR management will minimize potential conflicts over intellectual property streamlining decision-making regarding licensing, revenue sharing, or further development. It will also safeguard sensitive information shared during the collaboration, enabling all involved organizations to innovate confidently while maintaining competitive advantages. Researchers and organizations will be more willing to share ideas, data, and resources if they know their contributions will be protected and fairly recognized.

5.2 IPR in EVOLVE2CARE's external innovations

Similar to Innovation Management, the management of IPR in EVOLVE2CARE concerns those rights that are associated with the project's internal and external intellectual property. Task 5.2 (Technical, and Innovation Management) covers only the Intellectual Property Rights of the external participants (researchers and/or innovators) who utilise the services of Living Labs in the course of their experimentation activities. Other IPR - such as that for AccelUp - is addressed in T4.2 (Exploitation and IPR of AccelUP) and outside the scope of this deliverable. As stated in the task description, the overall goal of managing IPR for External Innovations is to ensure that researchers and innovators maintain ownership of their innovations during and after their residency at the Living Labs.

The researchers/innovators and Living Labs will be selected and matched for a residency according to the process set out in T2.2 (LLs, Innovators and Researchers Scouting and selection). During this process, an agreement (designed by Sploro for the purposes of EVOLVE2CARE) will be signed between both parties (innovator/researcher and Living Lab) to establish the terms and conditions of the residency. AV will assist with the design of this agreement to make certain that language protecting the IPR is included.

During the application and selection phases, the IPR protections will be stated in the FAQs and can be addressed via email/helpline should questions arise. Following selection and prior to the signing of the agreement, innovators or researchers who have questions regarding their IPR can discuss these with EVOLVE2CARE representatives. Any IPR-associated issues which may arise during the residency can be addressed at the mid-term check; in the case that urgent matters arise, consortium members will respond to researchers/innovators individually, as needed.

The IPR status will be included in the final assessment of each innovation at the end of the residency period. This is an integral portion of the KTH tool that will be used and forms one part of the overall evaluation we will conduct for researchers (see T3.4 Evaluation and advancement of the commercialization potential for Innovators/Researchers).

The correct approach to IPR management will also be addressed to wider audiences in the Training Program for Innovators (T2.4), and can be made available to Living Labs via the AccelUp platform and related standardization activities.

6 Advisory Board Activation

EVOLVE2CARE's External Advisory Board (EAB) has been chosen to provide strategic guidance, supporting the project's overall goals and ensuring quality and impact. Our EAB will offer expert advice on particular areas of concern to the project's main objective - identifying drivers and barriers to healthcare innovation. The board will help us steer the project, ensuring its success and societal relevance. In addition to providing us with expertise, our EAB members will also serve as amplifiers, assisting our communication efforts and spreading the word about EVOLVE2CARE through their networks.

6.1 Recruiting & Selection

Initial outreach was done to contacts in consortium partner's networks during the proposal phase. We aimed to include representatives from LLs, corporates, regulatory agencies, and the innovator/research community. Of the three individuals who agreed to take part at that time, two have restated their commitment to participate; the third is still uncertain due to business commitments. We have added a fourth member (committed) and are considering a fifth (should the third drop out). Each member has been briefed about the project's aims, and is able to carry out the duties.

6.2 Expectations

As a CSA (Coordination and Support Action), EVOLVE2CARE does not have weighty needs from its advisors. Nevertheless, we do not seek advisory members as "cosmetic" additions to our innovation management activities. EVOLVE2CARE's EAB is intended to play a substantive role, helping us to execute on our mission. This is especially important since they will not be compensated for their services.

We have asked the EAB to commit to three online meetings (one every six months) lasting up to 90' each. It is also our express desire to sponsor their attendance at our final event, should we have budgetary resources.

While this may seem like a negligible amount of time, we recognize that these are world-class individuals with a great deal of experience in their respective domains. It is therefore imperative that we make good use of their time. The structure for meetings will follow professional principles and practices:

- Meetings will be designed to leverage EAB members' expertise on specific questions and topics.
- Meetings will be scheduled based upon mutual availability (using doodle or

another online tool).

- Agendas and associated materials or briefings (to provide context) will be distributed in advance so there is time to review.
- Sessions will be recorded and a report generated and distributed following each meeting.

The EAB is slated to be finalised by March 2025 (M6), and has not yet engaged in any formal manner. Activities during the project’s lifetime will be reported in the final version of this deliverable in September 2026 (M24).

6.3 External Advisory Board Member Profiles

Table 5. External Advisory Board Members

<p>Costas Piliounis (GR)</p>	<p>Costas Piliounis is the Managing Director of PNValue, and a Professor of Management at Rome Business School. He has more than 30 years of management experience in the healthcare industry, specifically diagnostics and pharmaceuticals, previously as Corporate Vice President of NovoNordisk, and Chairman of the Board at BluSense. He is actively involved with the healthtech startups ReTouch (Thessaloniki, GR) and Biocos (Crete) and assists startups and spinoffs as an investor, advisor and consultant.</p>
<p>Maika Sabido (ES)</p>	<p>Maika Sabido, Project Manager at the Basque Health Cluster, a network partner of EIT Health Spain. Experience in research, development and manufacturing techniques for nano and microelectronic devices, nanostructuring of materials, ISOM., and UPM. Part of the MedLumics team in the development, manufacturing and characterization of a class III medical device with photonic technology. At the Basque Health Cluster she contributes to the growth of the Basque ecosystem of health and biosciences.</p>
<p>Cornel Amariei (RO)</p>	<p>Cornel Amariei is the Founder and CEO of dotLumen, a Romanian startup building glasses that help the blind live a better life. dotLumen has raised over €15M in private and public investments, including from the EIC. He has extensive technical experience in assistive mobility, sensors, and robotics, and regulatory expertise in ISO14155, ISO13485 / IEC62304, ISO14971, and Market Entry for Assistive Technologies & Medical Devices. (Participation pending as of 01/2025) <i>Participation pending.</i></p>

Katerina Zisaki (CH)

[Katerina Zisaki](#) demonstrates a multidisciplinary profile into the Quality and Regulatory Sector. She has more than 10 years experience in different roles from Quality Assurance and Regulatory Affairs through Management and Consulting, for the design, development, implementation, verification and validation and clinical evaluation as well as auditing of medical, IVDs and medicinal products. Katerina is a QMS auditor and technical expert in the field of medical devices for two EU Notified Bodies, while she contributes as Consultant to the IVD Prequalification team of WHO.

7 Technical, Innovation and IPR Progress, and Risks for their Exploitation

As this deliverable is being prepared in January 2025 (M4) of the project lifetime, there are no activities to report yet. A full accounting will be provided in the final version of *D5.3 Technical, IPR and Innovation Management*, due in September 2026 (M24).

Many of the activities which will inform the generation of templates and other materials for these activities are only just beginning. Please refer to Table 6. Evaluation of Innovators/Researchers' LL-supported experimentation for an explanation of the methodology and process that will provide the logic for the development of all materials.

Innovation and Exploitation Management Risks

If, at any point in time, an innovation-related risk emerges (described in Table 2), the IEM will call for an immediate project management meeting in order to discuss possible measures to mitigate the alleged risk.

Table 6. Tentative innovation management risks

Description of risk	Impact
State-of-the-art environment / project objectives lose relevance	High
Technological changes require significant redesign	High
Results produced by the experimentation(s) are not well exploitable	Medium
Living Labs do not have the correct resources to address the proposed experiments	High
Conflict between innovators/researchers and Living Labs about IPR	Low
Significant overlap in proposed experiments	Low

8 Conclusions, Risks, and next steps

The primary goals of this deliverable are to present the current framework for 1) evaluating and managing innovation potential, and 2) monitoring intellectual property rights of external innovations during the project's lifetime. Additionally, it provided some initial adaptations of the existing frameworks, such as the Innovation Radar, and KTH Innovation Readiness Level, which will be utilized to carry out the monitoring and management in the context of EVOLVE2CARE's Experimentations and Living Lab services execution. As this deliverable is being prepared in M4 of the project lifetime, there are no conclusions or risks to report yet. A full accounting will be provided in the final version of *D5.3 Technical, IPR and Innovation Management*, due in September 2026 (M24).